

Understanding Fact-Checking as a Global Phenomenon: Trends, Institutions, and Impact.

From 2004 to 2016.

Amr Sobhy
Birkbeck, University of London

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Abstract	2
Introduction	3
CHAPTER I. CONCEPTS AND LITERATURE REVIEW	6
A. Misinformation and Political Lying	6
B. Political Observatories and Technology	7
C. The Evolution in Studying Fact-checking	8
D. Fact-checkers: Journalists or Entrepreneurs?	9
E. Future of Fact-checking: A Post-factual World?	10
CHAPTER II. TRENDS OF FACT-CHECKING	13
A. First: Medium	13
B. Second: Target	16
C. Third: Type	17
CHAPTER III. INSTITUTIONS AND NETWORKS	21
A. International Fact Checking Network: Formation and Evolution	21
B. IFCN as an Institution	22
C. IFCN as a Transnational Advocacy Network	23
CHAPTER IV. IMPACT	26
A. Fact-checking: Slacktivism or Activism?	26
B. Fact-checking: Diverse Aims, Diverse Forms of Impact	27
C. Impact Assessment Frameworks	29
D. Impact Nationally and Transnationally	29
E. Fact-checking and Popular Culture	30
F. Case Study: From the MorsiMeter to the Global Meter	31
Conclusion	35
References	37

Abstract

Facts are at the core of the democratic process. Politicians neither always tell facts nor commit to what they pledge. Fact-checking refers to efforts focused on correcting misinformation, fighting falsehoods and bringing attention to facts and hard evidence. Fact-checking nowadays is mostly perceived to be a US-centered and journalistic phenomenon. However, in the recent few years, fact-checking has developed significantly and faster than the literature examining it. This paper explored the question of *How fact-checking evolved to become a global phenomenon with direct impact on national and transnational politics?* The author conducted a critical analysis of the global fact-checking ecosystem, stakeholders, and networks through data produced by Duke Reporters' Lab, International Fact Checking Network (IFCN) and interviews conducted in the annual fact-checking summit in Buenos Aires 2016. Throughout the paper, the author provided two main arguments on the globalisation of fact-checking; the distribution of the phenomenon worldwide and the evolution of the phenomenon to produce networks and institutions. By examining the first argument, a typology of different global trends of fact-checking is produced in relation to various lenses of types, targets and media. By examining the second argument, IFCN is studied as both a model of institutions and Transnational Advocacy Networks (TANs). The impact of this accelerating phenomenon is not restricted to tangible, immediate changes but also to a gradual cultural adoption of healthy skepticism towards news and politics. Finally, the paper concludes that fact-checking is no longer a US centered phenomenon. While this phenomenon is led by journalists, it is not exclusive to them. Civil society, entrepreneurs, and citizens also participate in the process of developing fact-checking.

Introduction

Misinformation is arguably one of the most striking features of the world as we know it today. The invention of the Internet has largely contributed to virtually eliminating the cost of acquiring large audiences and disseminating information. The Internet has reconstructed the information ecosystem, as it became, according to Clay Shirky (2009) - a prominent scholar in New York University-: “the first medium in history that has native support for groups and conversation at the same time” (Shirky, 2009). Phones have given us the opportunity to convey information to one another in a one-to-one model, while TV and print media disseminated information to everyone through a one-to-many model. Finally, the Internet came to disrupt this information model, giving us a many-to-many model. This has been the first time where media is natively equipped to support parallel and real-time multiple conversations at any given moment (Shirky, 2009). With a keyboard and an internet connection, everybody becomes a storyteller, and everybody becomes an information source. The result is not hard to imagine: the amount of misinformation the average person has to go through on a daily basis is staggering, from social media to email and from news websites to TV.

Identifying the truth within the political sphere has become a challenging task, in particular with the information overload. Politics is a very ripe field for misinformation. The common western joke that states: “how to tell a politician is lying? his lips move”, is an indication of a common perception of lying as a defining feature of politics historically. The accelerating rise of political lying globally has a major role in shaping world politics today. At the same time, democracy has been one of the direct victims of misinformation. A society that doesn't have the facts cannot understand, evaluate and make collective decisions that address its needs. Without facts and figures, decisions based on emotion and intuition become the norm. The case of the British referendum where citizens voted to exit the European Union, famously known as “Brexit”, as well as, the current (2016) American presidential race and the rise of Trump are instances of how misinformation play an important role in today's politics.

As a counteraction, some organizations and individuals have pledged to spread awareness against falsehoods by tracking evidence and facts. This has led to the birth of “Fact-checking”. Over the past few years, this phenomenon has been observed in many countries within different geographical areas and under different political systems. In every society, a group of people and organizations are eager to correct misinformation and bring awareness to hard facts in media and politics.

Fact-checking is argued to be more than a decade old and the year 2004 was called the year of fact-checking in the U.S because of the surprising rise of fact-checking (Amazeen, 2013), yet it is academically under-researched on the global level. Most of the literature on fact-checking is both US focused and journalism oriented. While fact-checking first emerged in the US where it is quite more popular than in other parts of the world, it is yet an accelerating phenomenon from Argentina to Egypt and from Bosnia and Herzegovina to South Africa. However, very few publications are tracking, capturing and analyzing fact-checking outside of the U.S. This paper aims to address this by looking into *How fact-checking has evolved to*

become a global phenomenon with direct impact on national and transnational politics?

This question brings about some sub-questions that further elaborate on the issue: What are the different trends of fact-checking globally? Is fact-checking exclusive for journalists? Does fact-checking constitute a manifestation of *Slacktivism* or does it bring about real impact? In an attempt to answer the main research question, I argue that the distribution and variation of fact-checking organisations around the world and the evolved networks and institutions have made fact-checking a global phenomenon aiming at scrutinizing accountability, improving journalism and nurturing democracy. Fact-checking is led by journalists however not exclusive to them, as civil society, entrepreneurs and citizens participate in the process of developing it.

Throughout the paper a systematic analysis for the current ecosystem would be conducted in pursuit of answering the sub-questions while testing the following four hypotheses:

- Fact-checking is a counter reaction for the spread of misinformation in the political sphere.
- Fact-checking is a global phenomenon that is US born.
- Fact-checking is led by -but not exclusive to- journalists.
- Fact-checking has both a national and transnational impact.

Fact-checking, is defined for the purpose of this paper as: efforts focused on correcting misinformation, fighting falsehoods and bringing attention to facts and hard evidence. By *global phenomenon*, it is meant that there is sufficient evidence for both distribution and evolution. Distribution as in both geographical sense; manifested in different geographical areas, and political sense: existing in different political systems. Evolution as in being able to grow from unorganized to a more institutionalized network.

In the first chapter, the different concepts necessary to understand the context through which fact-checking works will be explored; This includes understanding the political phenomenon of lying and the role technology plays in a democracy. In the following chapters, it will be argued that fact-checking is a global phenomenon through distribution and evolution. In the second chapter, the distribution argument will be discussed through a critical analysis of the current ecosystem of fact-checking globally, curating a typology based on medium (TV or online), target (media or politicians) and type (fact-checking, promise tracking or hybrid). In the third chapter, the evolution argument will be examined through analyzing the degree to which fact-checking has evolved institutionally. In particular, the focus is on the creation and development of the International Fact-Checking Network (IFCN) as a case study and it will be looked at it through the lens of Institutionalism and Transnational Advocacy Networks. Finally, the various aims of fact-checking and the challenges in its impact assessment will be explored. Its national and transnational will be explored through a short case-study.

Methodology

Testing the main argument as well as the hypotheses would be taking place through analysis of data produced by the Duke Reporters' Lab, the International Fact Checking Network's articles and publications on Poynter, as well as information published by fact-checkers themselves on their websites and in other interviews. In addition, semi-structured interviews were conducted at the annual fact-checking summit that took place in Buenos Aires, June 2016 where fact-checkers from 41 countries had gathered to discuss the growth and challenges of the fact-checking landscape worldwide. The author will also examine two case studies on the impact on the national and transnational level.

CHAPTER I

CONCEPTS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter will address the challenge of misinformation, the rise of political lying and the emergence of fact-checking as a counter phenomenon with the proliferation of political and media observatories. It will also discuss the role technology plays in the development of these concepts. Finally, a literature review of how fact-checking has been studied academically will be carried out.

Misinformation and Political Lying

“Everybody lies in Syria. State-media being the most obvious but also all sort of opposition factions spread lies to strengthen their position, inspire their followers and magnify their trauma” (Khattab, personal communication, August 4, 2016). This is what Dirar Khattab, one of the founders of Syria’s only fact-checking venture Ta’akkad (Verify) stated in his interview with me when asked about the motivation to start his fact-checking initiative.

Although politics in war zones may be radically different from other democratic and stable countries, the core of politics and media is quite similar. Bill Adair, founder of America’s top fact-checking venture Politifact gave a similar statement when asked the same question. He expressed how easy it is for politicians and media to voice false claims and go unchecked. The proliferation of technology has also made it easy for anyone with access to a keyboard and an internet connection to create a story that can go viral and shape public opinion (Adair, personal communication, June 10, 2016). Misinformation and lying is very common in any given political context.

The early work on bureaucracy tells us something about politicians. In Niskanen's view, there are two types of actors: bureaucrats and politicians. The relationship between them is one of bilateral monopoly. Politicians are the only consumers of bureaucratic products and are aiming to maximize the votes cast for them in the next election. On the other hand, bureaucrats are the only supplier of public goods and services and are aiming to maximize their agency's budget (Goodin, 1982, p. 25). This model has been criticized heavily especially by Goodin. However, the mere idea that politicians want to be re-elected cannot be ignored. Within the pursuit of getting elected and in the face of crises they may be tempted to lie or offer commitments they can't keep to appeal to voters.

A different approach to understanding lying in politics is presented by Mearsheimer (2011) who in his book “Why leaders lie” maintains that lying is acceptable behavior in politics. He adds: “Although lying is widely viewed as reprehensible behavior in ordinary life, it is acceptable conduct in international politics because there are sometimes good strategic reasons for leaders to lie to other countries and even to their people.” (Mearsheimer, 2011, p. 15). From a philosophical perspective, there are two ways to view lying: either from an absolutist view or a utilitarian one. Mearsheimer argues that philosophers like Kant for example, who come from absolutism background will always perceive lying as wrong. Contrary to Absolutists, Utilitarians can accept lying as an instrument of achieving “useful social

purpose” (Mearsheimer, 2011, p. 22). In his quantitative study, Armstrong-Taylor (2012) classifies politicians into two groups: “Honest politicians [who] always admit to the truth” and “opportunistic politicians” who may always consider options. Taylor maintains that “people are more likely to lie if innocence is more important than honesty” (Armstrong-Taylor, 2012, p. 22). Whether or not lying is a reasonable conduct in politics and regardless of the degree to which it is acceptable, fact-checking evolved from a journalistic practice to a counter-culture of political skepticism that increases the cost of lying for politicians. The use of technology was instrumental in the rise of fact-checking.

Political Observatories and Technology

The dramatic shifts in technology and evolution of social media platforms, as well as standalone new platforms, have had a vital influence on journalism, news and democracy worldwide. Technology has worked as an enabler for citizens to voice their causes, augment their views and attempt to hold governments accountable. For a long time, the production of public information was the job of journalists. Schudson (2010) has captured the progression of the public information ecosystem and the growth of political observatories as the world becomes increasingly complex to be reported by the conventional tools of journalism. However, for him, technological advancement is not in itself the reason for this rapid evolution of journalism and news. Technology did not operate in a vacuum; it’s the synergism between participatory democracy, civil rights movement and proliferation of nongovernmental organizations along with the Internet that has produced this change. (Schudson, 2010, p. 4)

Meanwhile, fact-checking has been taking place on existing social media platforms, as well as independent platforms specially made for fact-checking. Twitter, for example, is a leading platform that has been used by political journalists to amplify their fact-checking activities. Research by Coddington, Molyneux, and Lawrence (2014) involved a content analysis of political reporters’ Twitter discourse during the 2012 presidential debates and examined the degree to which fact-checking techniques were employed on Twitter and how much objectivity and professionalism were involved. Their conclusions were that Twitter was “conducive to some elements of fact-checking. But taken as a whole, data suggest that journalists and commentators posted opinionated tweets about the candidates’ claims more often than they fact-checked those claims.” (Coddington et al., 2014) Despite that, Twitter made it easy to start immediate and amplified discussions to fact-check false claims.

Another study by Guess (2015) used machine learning methods along with historical Twitter data to study how fact-checking endeavors occur on social media. He shows that “the amount of misinformation decreases over time as corrections make up a larger share of tweets relating to a particular claim” (Guess, 2015, p. 1). He also concluded that sentiment towards fact-checking taking place on Twitter “is likely to be positive than negative or neutral.” (Guess, 2015, p. 1). In conclusion, fact-checking has taken advantage of the evolution of democracy and technology together to produce stronger public debate and promote skepticism towards news and politicians.

The Evolution in Studying Fact-checking

One dominant theme in the fact-checking literature is a dual focus on the US as a place for study, and journalism as a theoretical vehicle and delivery method. Regarding the US, this can be explained by two arguments. First, fact-checking was arguably born in the United States where the oldest fact-checking initiative dates to 1995 (“Fact-checkers database”, 2016). Second, fact-checking flourishes with elections where statements and promises are in abundance as well as public interest. In that sense, the US elections breed a lot of fact-checking as promises are in abundance and worldwide public interest is very high. On the other hand, the argument of journalism being used as the primary theoretical vehicle for explaining fact-checking can be mostly understood through the present predominance of journalists-turned-fact checkers in the fact-checking global community. Nonetheless, this does not mean there are no other narratives that can explain the emergence of some other fact-checking organisations such as entrepreneurship, and civic engagement by citizens and civil society actors.

Amazeen (2013) studied the propagation of fact-checking within the US making a critical assessment of fact-checking in 2012 where fact-checking was attacked in the presidential race where she concluded that the principal goal of fact-checking should be to equip the public with the best possible proof to understand why a statement is deceiving. In addition, she maintains that fact-checking has profoundly changed journalism, the field from which it developed, by transforming its practices and prompting journalists to make politicians accountable (Amazeen 2013, p. 26). Similarly, Graves and Glaisyer (2012) explored the explosion of fact-checking in 2012 in a study under the title of “The Fact-Checking Universe in Spring 2012” where they concluded that non-partisan fact-checkers in the US had received attention equally from the left and the right. Also, fact-checking is no longer exclusive to politics but goes beyond to include other areas of debate on science, economics, health, and climate change. (Glaisyer and Graves, 2012, p. 17).

Graves, Nyhan and Reifler (2016) repeatedly wrote about different perspectives of fact-checking. They similarly investigated why journalists fact-check, concluding that fact-checking is mainly driven by “professional motives within journalism” (Graves et al 2016, p. 0). They also wrote about the diffusion of fact-checking and its understanding as a journalistic innovation and suggested that fact-checking growth “may be more directly attributable to the efforts of journalistic and academic entrepreneurs” (Graves et al 2015, p. 16). Furthermore, Spivak (2011) in *American Journalism Review* maintained that the political environment has influence over flourishing or declining of fact-checking. In a bitter political situation where allegations and doubts are of constant increase, more fact-checking organisations are expected to operate. (Spivak, 2011)

When it comes to quantitative studies, the literature is limited. Brendan Nyhan and Jason Reifler carried out a few quantitative experiments. In their publication “The Effects of Fact-checking Threat”, they conducted a field experiment in the US during the 2012 elections campaign assessing the change in the behavior of legislators when they are threatened by fact-checking. They concluded that the threat of fact-checking has managed to influence the behavior of state legislators. They elaborate:

“We found that legislators who were sent reminders that they are vulnerable to fact-checking were less likely to receive a negative PolitiFact rating or have the accuracy of their statements questioned publicly than legislators who were not sent reminders.” (Nyhan and Reifler 2013)

On a different front, Guess (2015) assessed the growth of fact-checking on Twitter by conducting sentiment analysis where he concluded that fact-checkers' role on Twitter was to produce material with which Twitter users confront false beliefs. Regardless of the fact that it is hard to judge whether these beliefs have changed or not, he stated: the messages they promote appear to help make the debate on the platform more accurate.

Fact-checkers: Journalists or Entrepreneurs?

Fact-checking can be widely regarded as an evolution in journalism practice, especially in the US. Like other similar innovations, fact-checking “ties new reporting techniques to an appeal to longstanding journalistic values” (Graves et al, 2015). In 2003, FactCheck.org began operation by fact-checking issues of national interest. The birth of PolitiFact in 2007 could be regarded as a critical step within this trend, the flagship brand of fact-checking. Finally, the Washington Post's Fact Checker rose to prominence in 2011 (American Press Institute, 2015). However, that does not entirely mean it is always journalists who start and lead fact-checking organisations. In his interview with International Journalists' Network, Alexios Mantzarlis, the Director of IFCN, stated: “In many other parts of the world, it isn't even journalists leading fact-checking efforts, but organized civil society groups frustrated with the media not fulfilling its role in scrutinizing public claims” (Ricchiardi, 2016). This claim applies to cases like Egypt, Bosnia, and Iran. The Egyptian MorsiMeter was founded by two entrepreneurial citizens who were frustrated with the status quo and wanted to expand democracy beyond the ballot box. Bosnia's Zašto ne (Why Not): a Sarajevo-based nongovernmental organization that focuses on civic engagement and government accountability through technology was founded by Darko Brkan, an electrical engineer. Iran's RouhaniMeter was founded by Ali Bangi, a Ph.D. Candidate in the University of Toronto's Department of Political Science. The examples are numerous and reflect a trend of growing civic skepticism towards politics.

Through journalism, fact-checking helps to create a culture of “factual disputes”(Graves et al., 2015) and while each fact-checking organisations may have a relatively small audience, the outcome is amplified when the culture starts to spread. Other reporters start to engage in fact-checking themselves making it more likely that those who repeat falsehoods will probably be challenged by other journalists (Graves et al., 2015). Journalism affiliation in fact-checking can be either through direct association with news or media establishments or it can be manifested in the background of fact-checkers. Regarding the first, a comparison was drawn regarding the affiliations of the different fact-checking organisations in Figure (1), out of the 157 fact-checking organizations nearly 31% of those are direct affiliates to journals or news websites. This clearly shows how journalism and fact-checking go hand-in-hand. However, it also proves that there are a lot of opportunity for fact-checkers outside the journalism ecosystem.

Figure 1. Affiliation of fact-checking organisations. Produced from *Fact-checkers database*, by Duke Reporters' Lab, 2016.

One recurring theme when it comes to motivations behind starting fact-checking organisations is political polarization and quality of public debate, which influences both journalists and non-journalists. Tai Nalon, a Brazilian political reporter who started Aosfatos, a Brazilian fact-checking organisation, stated in her interview: “people have disbelief in politicians.” She added

“we are in the middle of a very polarized society; I think you have to mediate a very scarce debate. There are people who want to debate and exchange ideas and they are more moderate in the middle of a polarized context. These people are eager read facts and dig through trustworthy information”. (Nalon, personal communication, June 10 2016)

Laura Zommer, an Argentine woman who leads Chequeado, an independent fact-checking media organizations based in Argentina, answered the same question similarly: “we lived a very polarized context in terms of politics and media debate. We created Chequeado to improve the quality of public debate, and if we improve the quality of our public debate that’s good for our democracy.” (Zommer, personal communication, June 10, 2016)

Future of Fact-checking: A Post-factual World?

In his opinion piece, Paul Krugman (2011), the Nobel laureate in economics and a distinguished professor, shared his concerns about moving towards a world where truth doesn’t weigh significantly in the course of actions. He was explicitly critical of Romney’s campaign attacking Obama with series of attacks that are entirely based on falsehood. His main question was “Won’t Mr. Romney pay a price for running a campaign based entirely on falsehoods? He obviously thinks not, and I’m afraid he may be right.” (Krugman, 2011). In his analysis, this is due to the way media works in the U.S. He states:

“most of the news media will feel as though their reporting must be balanced, which means that every time they point out that a Republican lied they have to match it with a comparable accusation against a Democrat — even if what the Democrat said was actually true or, at worst, a minor misstatement.” This has

led him to describe Romney's campaign as "The Post-Truth Campaign."(Krugman, 2011)

"Why Facts No Longer Matter" is the title of an introductory chapter by Farhad Manjoo (2008) in an attempt to delve into the dilemma through a book called "True enough". Although it is mainly addressing the American society, the trend applies on a global scale. His book tries to capture the radical transformation in the way Americans are thinking about the media and news. His argument is that the majority of Americans are no longer holding different opinions about what they should do towards certain policies and events but rather what is actually happening. As he puts in words "we're now fighting over competing versions of reality."

Manjoo (2008) attributes this shift to a few reasons. First, what he calls "selective exposure" which is a form of coping mechanisms that psychologically arise when people are confronted with information that clashes with some of the core beliefs they hold. The theory feeds off a more famous theory of "cognitive dissonance". In essence, his argument is "giving people information that runs contrary to their core beliefs doesn't necessarily prompt them to reconsider their ideas. Sometimes it prompts a deaf ear."(Manjoo, 2008) This explains how stories with scarce evidence can now easily invade and dominate the political discourse.

It doesn't stop there, David Sirota (2007) officially welcomed us to "the Post-Factual Era". In his article in the Huffington Post he downplays the importance of facts and emphasises the importance of money and power. He compares the world of business to that of politics, which works in an entirely reversed way. In his understanding, in business those who make the right decisions are rewarded and promoted while in politics those making the wrong decisions are those who are rewarded and celebrated. He gives examples of the Iraq war, where "most of the major pundits who led the cheering section for the war have been rewarded with promotions, while those writers who actually accurately predicted the war as a disaster have been cast aside like pieces of garbage." Sirota (2007) believes that we are witnessing the rise of what he calls "post-factual" as a replacement for what used to be "reality-based community". In this era, dialogues relying on too little evidence are celebrated as the most right ones. (Sirota, 2007)

This is all relevant to two major global events at the moment, the Brexit and the US presidential electoral race. While both countries are too distant geographically, the two events bear so much similarity. Both witnessed what we can call, using Sirota's language, "post-factual" manifestations. In the UK and more especially in the Brexit referendum, the Exit camp won with 52% vs 48% for the Remain camp. The main arguments turned to be factually distorted. FullFact, a UK fact-checking organization, has curated a series of videos on YouTube ("Factchecked", 2016) debunking the claims one by one. However, the playlist has only 3,101 views at the time of writing this paper and at the end the Leave camp won, despite the facts not being on their side. Ipsos published a paper on the "Public misperceptions about the EU and how it affects life in the UK", which concludes that vital misperceptions about the consequences of leaving the EU prevailed in the referendum. (Ipsos, 2016)

In the U.S, Trump managed to get the Republican nomination. According to Politifact, around 71% of the fact-checked statements of Trump ranged from (Mostly false to Pants on Fire). Despite the falsehood, he managed to secure the Republican

ticket and move on to compete for the presidency of the U.S ("Donald Trump's file", 2016). While this all seems quite disappointing, Mantzralis (2016) has a different view. He maintains that it is a historical habit, at any given moment in history, to be complaining about the deteriorating politics and reality conflict. He alternatively sees this as a coping mechanism for commentators who are in shock with the fact that the political reality is completely different from the "liberal-cosmopolitan worldview". For him, it's "easier to explain them away by painting 2016 as an apocalyptic "post-truth" era where people are just not getting the importance of facts." (Mantzralis, 2016)

Mantzralis has two studies to back him up. First, a study by Brendan Nyhan and Jason Reifler (2012) under the title of "The Effects of Fact-checking Threat Results from a Field Experiment in the States" concluded that politicians on the state level who were put under the threat of being fact-checked turned out to be less likely to make false claims (Reifler and Nyhan, 2012). Another one, by Bullock et al. (2015), under the title of "Partisan Bias in Factual Beliefs about Politics" suggested that much of the partisan split on essential facts may be over exaggerated and in their words "the apparent gulf in factual beliefs between members of different parties may be more illusory than real" (Bullock et al, 2015, p. 520)

In conclusion, the gap in the literature suggests little focus on fact-checking from a global perspective. Most fact-checking studies are conducted on US audience and are about US politics. The evolution of fact-checking as a global trend remains heavily untapped. Also, while it sometimes may seem that facts are becoming less relevant every now and then, facts seem to still have effects on the dynamics of the political landscape

CHAPTER II

TRENDS OF FACT-CHECKING

This chapter discusses fact-checking as a global phenomenon through focusing on the distribution of fact-checking organisations across the world. A typology will be curated, and a classification of fact-checking organisations on three primary levels will be done; medium, target, and type. The analysis would be taking place on data produced by Duke Reporters' Lab and IFCN at Poynter, in addition to the semi-structured interviews conducted at the annual fact-checking summit that was held in Buenos Aires, June 2016.

Fact-checking can no longer be addressed through the compact lens of American politics; it grew far beyond the borders of the US. From Tunisia to Brazil and from Canada to India, fact-checkers are learning from each other and are driving accountability and journalism. Until the moment of writing this paper, the author is unaware of any typology attempts made to capture the global trends of fact-checking and the different forms it takes around the world. Hence, thinking of a classification system should allow us to recognize similar features between various fact-checking organisations and help us grasp the bigger picture. A simple typology can divide fact-checking organisations into groups based on medium, target, and type. The first looks through the lens of the platform used to fact-check whether it was online (Internet) or offline (TV and print). The second looks at the target of fact-checking whether it was politicians/authority figures or media. Finally, The third looks at the type of fact-checking activity; is it purely fact-checking or promise tracking or mix of both.

First: Medium

The first parameter used to classify fact-checking organisations is the medium or channel fact-checkers use to deliver their work. Today, by and large, the work of fact-checkers is distributed between two major mediums, TV and the Internet.

TV.

TV is a powerful but not a very popular medium for fact-checking. “Fact-checking is mostly done online. Fact-checking in its current guise is a product of the internet age internationally, the vast majority of fact-checkers operate primarily online. Only 3 out of 45 organizations in a recent survey are TV-first” (Mantzaris, 2016). Different mediums mean different audience as well as different challenges. Some believe that although TV is losing much of its viewership to the Internet, by and large, it still enjoys a bigger audience. It was only recently in the US in 2014 that the Internet became officially bigger than cable (Wohlsen, 2014, para. 1). However, in other countries, the image may be quite different. For example in Egypt, according to Gallup, TV is the most popular source of information. It is estimated that 98.8% of all Egyptians maintain at least one TV set in their household. On the other hand, home Internet access is around 25.5%, with one in every four Egyptians

having internet access. (Gallup, 2013, p. 1). Hence, TV might have a far bigger impact depending on the country.

In his Article, “Can the worldwide boom in digital fact-checking make the leap to TV?” Mantzarlis (2016) justifies why fact-checkers resort to TV relating this to its distinctive form of storytelling and the big audience they are bound to reach through it. Today there are a few TV fact-checking experiences that produce regular stand-alone segments which include UK’s Channel 4, Italy’s Rai 2, and Korea’s JTBC (Mantzarlis, 2016).

Perhaps the best case-study for TV fact-checking is “El Objetivo” with its fact-checking segment “Pruebas de Verificación” airing every Sunday evening on Spanish La Sexta. Ramon Salaverría at the University of Navarra stated that “El Objetivo is the most salient example of fact-checking journalism in Spain.” According to Mantzarlis (2015), there is at least an estimation of 1.5 million viewers who follow the show. (Mantzarlis, 2015)

Another example of how powerful live TV fact-checking can be is a story by Jeta Xharra of Balkan Investigative Reporting Network. She vocalized the inability of the government in Kosovo to force people to pay their electricity bills creating a massive crisis. Officials were hosted on a live TV show and asked about their commitment to paying their bills, they all firmly confirmed that they had paid all dues. Instantaneously, she fact-checks their statements and shows their actual bills which are all long past due. According to her, a reported surge in paying the energy bills was noticed after that episode (Xharra, 2016).

Little of the potential of TV fact-checking is currently tapped, as mentioned earlier, “Only 3 out of 45 organizations in a recent survey are TV-first” (Mantzarlis, 2015). The author identified three primary reasons on why online fact-checking is more popular than its TV counterpart namely, lower barriers to entry online as compared to TV, better feedback cycle, and user-engagement potential, and finally TV needs careful adaptation.

First, with regards to low barriers to entry, it is relatively easy to set-up a website and start fact-checking organisations with trivial to low cost involved as opposed to TV. Although there are no dedicated content management systems (CMS) that are tailored specifically for this purpose, use of ready-made CMS like Wordpress makes the process relatively easy. However, many fact-checkers build their own CMS from scratch. Compare that to the difficulty of getting airtime, the crew involved, and the disproportionately high cost.

Second, Better feedback cycle and user engagement: having a website on the internet you can track almost everything which gives you insightful knowledge on how to sharpen your strategies and better address the right audience. Questions like where do your users come from? What are they exactly looking for? How much time do they spend? And where do they spend it? can be easily asked and answered and even for free. Communication can also be a two-way process. People can comment, share, like in real-time. TV, on the other hand, seems more of a monolog except for phone calls which are harder to make and involves more exposure and less anonymity from the individual compared to the safety of anonymity made possible by the Internet.

Third, Careful adaptation is needed on TV: Simple presentation of facts on TV is not a guarantee that it will do well. A lot of energy is required to make it more engaging and increase the chance it resonates with the audience. Mantzarlis during a panel discussion on TV fact checking in Sarajevo stated: “A great fact check doesn’t automatically do well on TV” (Mantzarlis, 2016). Then upon request of further clarification through email communication, he added, “ it must be translated into the right language. The way US TV does fact-checking isn't particularly engaging.” (Mantzarlis, personal communication, 2016)

However, despite the difficulties involved with TV fact checking it is yet of a high degree of importance globally. We can’t ignore the potential impact for TV as it can reach more audience and more effectively discredit lying politicians. Mantzarlis confirms this using the US as an example: “Even in countries with vigorous digital fact-checking, weak TV fact-checking can allow some candidates a free pass.” (Mantzarlis, 2016)

Online.

Online fact-checking remains the most common form of fact-checking. Arguably, the most influential online fact-checking website is the truth-o-meter by PolitiFact. Bill Adair, the creator of PolitiFact and Truth-O-Meter and a professor at the Sanford School of Public Policy at Duke University, stated in the interview when asked about his motivation to start fact-checking, that it came out of frustration of how the role of media changed traditionally compared to now in the digital world. He then elaborates:

“The media acted as a useful filter in filtering out the crazy stuff. And in the analogue age ... to be responsible, you don’t report things that you checked out and found are not true. In the digital age, what changed is that there was no longer a filter, because there was a multitude of new ways anyone with a crazy idea, had a microphone to spread a falsehood or something ridiculously false.... as I begin to realize that the dynamics of information has changed I realized that the media had a new role, instead of acting as a filter for the inaccurate stuff, we needed to actively tell people what was inaccurate. In the words of my colleague and the editor of the Tampa Bay Times, Neil Brown: “consumers wanted an honest broker”. (Adair, personal communication, 2016)

Now, and according to the about page of Politifact, on a daily basis, their editors engage in a rigorous exercise of fact-checking by examining statements by the president, presidential candidates, Congress members, governors, mayors, lobbyists and in general people involved in American politics ("About PolitiFact", 2016). They do the necessary research and finally, provide a rate of accuracy. The model of the Truth-O-Meter has been picked up by many other organizations and individuals in different countries across the globe. While the methodologies and scale of assessment may differ, the concept is rather the same. Their pioneering and inspiration are widely recognized in the community of fact-checkers.

As the Internet was the place of misinformation, it’s increasingly becoming the location of correction as well. However, one cannot equate the exposure of both. Fact-checking being always in the position of pursuing damage control means there will always be damage and victims of misinformation; it only strives to lessen the

damage and promote a general culture of skepticism. In achieving this online fact-checking employs different rating methodologies. Scales used in assessment can vary from binary to five rating scales. Binary scales are straightforward and easily understood by everyone. Examples of scales include true to false / achieved to not achieved / Fulfilled to Not Fulfilled. Three rating scales are usually more descriptive but still easy to follow. For example True to False, including "can't be verified" as in Irish Journal. Achieved, In Progress and not Achieved as in Egyptian MorsiMeter.com. Completed, Failed and In Progress as in Ukrainian slovoidilo.ua ("Global Fact-checking Sites, 2016).

Sometimes two and three rating scales are not enough. That's where we find four and five rating scales. An example of a four rating scale is what Michigan Truth Squad uses: Flagrant foul, Regular foul, Warning, No foul. An example of a five rating scale is what De Correspondent's Factcheck use, where options ranging from uncheckable ("niet te checken"), to entirely false to partly true/partly false to entirely true in Dutch exist ("Global Fact-checking Sites, 2016).

Second: Target

The second filter in this typology is to look at fact-checking organisations through the perspective of the intended target. In other words, what is the scope of fact-checking? Who are they targeting? Usually, fact-checking plays along one of the following themes. Either the focus is on one key politician, a group of politicians or media.

The first type; focusing on one key politician: this is more popular in promise-tracking style fact-checking and usually the name of the politician is the part of the name of the initiative. For example, Morsi Meter monitoring Egyptian president Mohamed Morsi in Egypt 2012. Rouhani Meter, following Iranian President Hassan Rouhani in Iran. SebsiMeter, watching the performance of Essebsi of Tunisia, and finally Trudeau meter of Canada.

Figure 2. Targeting of fact-checking organisations. Produced from *Fact-checkers database*, by Duke Reporters' Lab, 2016.

This pie chart compares the number of fact checking bodies which target one politician to those that target more than one (including a range of officials or media). fact-checking organisations which target one politician make up about 4% of total known fact-checking organisations by analyzing data collected by Duke Reporters' Lab.

The second type, focusing on a Group of Politicians, is not narrowly focused on one key personality, but rather a group of political figures, political groups, and candidates. Examples of this type include FactCheker India, which monitors political statements at large, and also Istinomer of Serbia.

The final type, focusing on media: this sort of fact-checking organisations is focused on claims propagated through media rather than being focused on one key politician or a group of authority figures. In other words, they target stories that are circulating and getting attention through different types of media. The more the story circulates, the more the need to fact-check it. Examples of projects under this category include fact-checking of Macedonia, a project supported by the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) that reviews the accuracy and fairness of media reports, Ta'kad (Verify) of Syria, and DaBegad of Egypt. The problem with media being flooded with falsehoods and inaccurate stories is that it misinforms people immediately, even if they don't read the details or examine the coherence of the different threads of the story. Scrolling through one's Facebook timeline is sufficient to consume numerous false stories and even propagate them without careful consideration. An experiment done by Egyptian AkhbarMeter, an early stage media fact-checking initiative explores this idea by writing an entirely fabricated title and thumbnail about a story regarding inflammatory Egyptian politics and giving it a boost on Facebook. The link if clicked would lead to a page that would explain that this is an experiment and the title was fabricated to distinguish those who click and read more from those who just interact with the post without further examination. The result: the post received 3.8 thousand likes and 835 shares and 450+ comments. This means that false stories can influence a lot of people without even reading them thoroughly. They can even interact with the story and propagate it more without fully understanding what it is about.

Third: Type

So far, the big umbrella of fact-checking in practice accommodates three types of fact-checking organisations. The pure fact-checking style, the promise-tracking, and the hybrid. Out of 157 fact-checking entities, 42 are providing promise-tracking functionality, which constitutes up to 26.6% as opposed to 73.4% that provide fact-checking functionality only.

Figure 3. Types of fact-checking organisations. Produced from *Fact-checkers database*, by Duke Reporters' Lab, 2016.

The theory of change involved in the two types is of certain difference. While pure fact-checking organisations focus on the value of “facts”, promise tracking bodies rest almost solely on the value of “attention” which accountability is a byproduct of. In an age of information bloat, we find it hard to keep our attention focused on one thing. This provides an opportunity for politicians to promise things they will not deliver and then twist the facts later. Promise trackers act as guards that provide a centralized and specialized focal point of analysis that harnesses the power of attention. Hence, without attention, it is easy for politicians to be unaccountable. Attention keeps promises in the public short and long memory. In one way it acts as means to debate on how these promises are realized (short-term) and in another way it becomes archived for re-visiting in the future (long-term). Fact-checking is about examining statements, doing the required research and coming up with a verdict. On the other hand, promise tracking is about watching pledges and actively following up on the status of each pledge.

Below is a comparison between the different countries with fact-checking organisations offering a promise tracking functionality (whether dedicated or hybrid) and their democracy index status provided by Freedom House Index (Freedom in the World, 2016). Out of the 26 countries where promise tracking bodies operate, three are classified as not free, ten are classified as partly free and thirteen as free. This shows that even countries that are classified as non-free and partially free can manage to operate promise tracking bodies. In the Iranian example of RouhaniMeter, it is operated from exile in Canada. Two Iranian students started the RouhaniMeter inspired by the MorsiMeter of Egypt, which is also classified as non-free at the moment. Hence, fact-checking is not only possible in free countries, but It is also much needed in non-free and partially free countries for a few reasons.

Figure 4. Freedom index of countries with promise trackers.

First, countries with “not free” and “partly free” rankings are usually either closed systems “Iran”, or pseudo and emerging democracies “Egypt, Afghanistan, Albania and Bosnia and Herzegovina”. In these countries there is a lot of focus on the procedures of democracy, but not necessarily the essential core values. Having parties, programs, and electoral process is important. However, these programs are usually similar to one another; there is no real distinction between parties and politicians fail to make specific, measurable, attainable, realistic and time-bounded promises. Saffon and Urbinati (2013) echoed these concerns where a departure from the focus on procedures to outcomes is taking a place in the literature of democratic theory. They elaborate: “Partly as an attempt to distance itself from Schumpeterian democracy, normative political theory began to focus less on the democratic process itself and more on the morally correct disposition of its participants and the quality of its outcomes” (Saffron and Urbinati, 2013, p. 443).

Janda (2010) maintains that procedural view of democracy misses a core component of democracy which is responsiveness.

“Responsiveness states that elected representatives should respond to public opinion. They should do what a majority of the citizens want, regardless of what that is. This principle is unsettling to some people, who fear the enactment of “undemocratic” decisions by responding to majority rule” (Janda, 2010)

Responsive, per se, is a by product of accountability and public debate to which fact-checking contributes.

Second, in emerging democracies, holding elected politicians accountable is challenging and showing them that what they promise will not be forgotten the very next day may push them to make an effort to change their political rhetoric and pay attention to what they promise. Promise trackers are great ways to move the democratic conversation beyond electoral politics and the ballot box. In emerging and pseudo-democracies citizens are led to believe that the boundaries of democracy end by the polls. There is little focus on the process of accountability and citizen right and duty to follow up on the promises of elected officials, rely on facts and change their vote in next elections accordingly. When promise-trackers are successful, they play a civic education role in teaching citizens indirectly about what is within their means from a substantive democratic perspective.

Both pure fact-checking and promise-tracking help keep people informed. On one hand, fact-checking organisations are monitoring statements of political actors/media/journals, research the facts, analyze each statement and provide an opinion on the truthfulness of the statement. On the other hand, promise trackers monitor pledges made by officials and act as a form of collective memory. They both help to drive more accountability; fact-checking by promoting facts and focus on improving journalism, promise trackers, on the other hand, rely on the collective attention as means to accountability. The audience of fact-checking websites is usually left with a verdict based on the analysis provided on the degree of truthfulness of the statement. On the other hand, promise trackers on their basic level, often, provide just statistical facts and leave it up to the public to make their judgment on what that means in terms of the binaries of good and bad, success or failure. For instance, the Obama-o-meter which monitors the pledges of Obama in the U.S provided the following graph:

Figure 5. Breakdown of the promises of Obama by Politifact. Copyright [2015] by PolitiFact.

The graph shows that Obama has kept 45% of his promises, compromised quarter of them, and broken 22%. ("The Obameter Pledge-o-Meter", n.d.) However, it doesn't go beyond this factual approach and uses it to judge whether Obama did good or bad, was he successful or not? This is left to people to debate. Since the definitions of success or failure can be very subjective, it needs to be left out of this scope. In conclusion, throughout this typology, I offered a few ways to look at the diversity of the fact-checking scene today and the different forms it takes globally by examining three parameters, the medium, the target and the type of fact-checking organisations.

CHAPTER III

INSTITUTIONS AND NETWORKS

This chapters focuses on the evolution argument and examines the globalism of the fact-checking phenomenon by exploring the degree to which it has evolved into an institutionalized movement. In particular, the study strives to look at the International Fact-Checking Network as both an institution and a Global Transnational Advocacy Network (TAN).

There are many competing schools of institutionalism as a theory including historical, rational choice and sociological institutionalism. They define institutions differently, and they look at the relationships between the actors involved from different perspectives. Historical Institutionalism would identify institutions broadly as “formal or informal procedures, routines, norms and conventions embedded in the organizational structure of the polity or political economy.” (Hall, 1996, p. 6) Rational Choice Institutionalism, which emerged at the same time as historical institutionalism but in relative isolation capitalized on conceptual and analytical instruments of what became later known as new organizational economics. Two analytical concepts in Rational Choice Institutionalism (RCI) are important in understanding institutions: transaction cost economics and theories of agency. First, RCI looks at the emergence of institutions as a form of reducing the transaction costs of performing a particular activity without such an institution in place. Second, RCI focuses on the institutional mechanisms whereby “principals can monitor and enforce compliance on their agents” (Hall, 1996, p. 11). In conclusion there are two core functions that are tied to institutions through a Rational Choice Institutionalism perspective: efficiency; by managing information flow and minimizing transaction cost, and regulation by putting rules in place that improve collective decision-making. Next, the formation and evolution of the International Fact Checking Network as an example of an institution bred through the growth of the phenomenon and will argue it performs the two functions would be thoroughly examined.

International Fact Checking Network: Formation and Evolution

In June 2014, the London School of Economics witnessed the first gathering of fact-checkers worldwide for the very first time which brought together about 40 fact-checkers from different spots around the world such as South Africa, Italy, Great Britain, India, the United States, South America, Egypt and Eastern Europe. The main idea behind this gathering was to discuss both growth and challenges around fact-checking.

The biggest outcome proposed within this gathering was to form a loose network to bring together fact-checkers worldwide. The network's bio on Twitter maintains that It is focused on studying & discussing fact-checking as a journalistic instrument (“IFCN”, 2016). The following version of the conference in London, 2015 has witnessed the official birth of the International Fact Checking Network (IFCN). In September 2015, Poynter named Fact-Checking Expert Alexios Mantzarlis Director and editor of the new International Fact-Checking Network, Based at its Florida Headquarters. Fast forward to June 2016, the yearly London gathering has

moved to South America, specifically to Buenos Aires to unfold the third version of Global Fact-checking Summit which included representatives of more than a 100 projects from around 41 countries.

Tim Franklin, president of Poynter, the institution that has created the network- believes that the network was created out of a commitment to their mission. In his words, “Poynter’s mission is to advance journalistic excellence that serves democracy, and I can’t think of a more appropriate or important initiative than the International Fact-Checking Network” (“Poynter Names Fact-Checking Expert Alexios Mantzarlis Director and Editor of the New International Fact-Checking Network, Based at its Florida Headquarters | Poynter”, 2015). Abbas Adel, co-founder of the Morsi Meter and member of the network upon being asked about his perception of the value he is getting he stated: “It has created a sense of community and support. It also makes it easy to share experiences or get immediate help and support when needed” (Adel, personal communication, 2016)

The group didn’t arise out of thin air, as there is a steady growth of fact-checking organisations around the world. The following graph captures the growth of fact-checking organizations over the past five years.

Figure 6. Growth of fact-checking between 2012. Produced from compiling data from Fact-checkers database, by Duke Reporters' Lab, 2016.

This bar chart illustrates the total number of fact-checking organizations captured by the Duke Reporters' Lab. The total number of organizations has jumped from 57 in 2012 to a total of 157 by 2016 in 55 countries. The chart reflects a clear upward trend year to year and reflects a need to organize.

IFCN as an Institution

The IFCN can be looked upon as an institution because it performs two functions. First, managing information flow and minimizing transaction cost by acting as a unified hub and single-point of entry to the fact-checking world. This can be seen in the following examples: First, The IFCN organizes a yearly meeting to gather fact-checkers around the world to discuss most relevant challenges to the

fact-checking community. The gathering also serves as a networking hub. Without this gathering, barriers of finding, communicating with other fact-checkers would be immense. Second, The IFCN runs an email group for communicating, seeking support, exchange of information, one which the author of this study has repeatedly used to contact fact-checkers around the world. Third, The IFCN connects fact-checking experts to those who are newly joining the movement to help them quickly get on board and do their work efficiently. Finally, The IFCN writes and publishes articles constantly bringing fact-checking to the forefront of the public debate.

Second, advancing the fact-checking initiative while setting standards for what makes a good fact-checker. The network doesn't regulate fact-checking per se, as it is not up to them to approve or disapprove other fact-checkers work. However, it strives to standardize fact-checking practices globally. This can be demonstrated in the following examples: First, in Buenos Aires, a call for developing a code of principles listing the best practices that conscientious fact-checkers should aspire to took place, today the code is ready and is being signed upon by various fact-checking organisations. Alexis Mantzarlis, IFCN Director, clarified in an email communication: "Most of us already have methodologies, correction policies, mission statements, etc. and this in many ways just codifies our common goals. The code would guide those who want to differentiate fact-checking from biased or sloppy "faux-checking". The latter risks undermining our work and further increasing distrust in the potential of journalism to keep public figures accountable." (Mantzarlis, personal communication, 2016). Second, also in Buenos Aires, Global Fact 3 summit, The possibility of launching an International Fact-Checking Day was entertained and later acted upon internally. Mantzarlis explains: "an International Fact-Checking Day as an opportunity to drum up citizen participation in fact-checking. The goal isn't so much to celebrate our work as much as to inspire others to jump on the ship and help us all out." (Mantzarlis, personal communication, 2016).

In conclusion, from a Rational Choice Institutionalism perspective, the IFCN exhibits two critical functions of institutions. On one hand, it increases the efficiency of the fact-checking community and the transactions taking place within. On the other hand, it shows some form of regulation through promoting codes of ethics and guidelines.

IFCN as a Transnational Advocacy Network

In addition to looking at IFCN through an institutionalist theoretical lens, It is possible to attempt to understand IFCN within another theoretical narrative of transnational advocacy. Keck and Sikkink (1998) sought to drive attention to the role transnational advocacy networks plays in global politics. According to them, networks are "forms of organization characterized by voluntary, reciprocal and horizontal patterns of communication and exchange" (Keck and Sikkink, 1998). Advocacy captures the uniqueness of these transnational networks as "they are organized to promote causes, principled ideas and norms, and often involve individuals advocating policy changes that can not be easily linked to their interests" (Keck and Sikkink, 1998)

These networks have shared values and frequently exchange information and services. (Keck and Sikkink, 1998). For IFCN, these common values are best articulated and captured by Angie Holan (2016), the Politifact editor in her article:

“What do fact-checkers around the world have in common?” where she suggested they are: transparency, fairness, thoroughness, independence and accountability (Holan, 2016).

Transparency is emphasized in the way fact-checkers reach their conclusions, by always pointing out to all resources and points of references needed. Fairness, in using the same methodology on everyone in an evidence-based manner. Thoroughness, through the fact that it is a rigorous process that involves finding the evidence, even in unusual places then consulting experts if needed to evaluate it. Independence by checking all sides of the debate and avoiding any influence from any stakeholder and finally accountability by “holding politicians accountable by letting them know they will be fact-checked, especially when they make inaccurate statements”. (Holan, 2016).

International networking is costly due to various sets of reasons that include geographical distance, difference in languages and variance of cultures, in addition to communication and travel cost (Keck and Sikkink, 1998). These obstacles do not encourage cooperation and network formation. Hence the proliferation of networks must be explained. Keck and Sikkink (1998) maintained that transnational advocacy networks (TANs) arise when “political entrepreneurs” believe that networking will help them advance their causes, and when conferences create areas for forming networks. Which was the case with IFCN, when Bill Adair announced the idea in London as a platform for networking and advancing fact-checking globally.

Tarrow and Della Porta defined transnational activism and collective action as “the coordinated international campaigns on the part of networks of activists against international actors, other states, or international institutions.” (as cited in Caouette, 2006). In that light, the IFCN can be considered an actor coordinating a continuous global campaign against political lying and encouraging the effective use of journalism as a tool to hold politicians accountable and keep democracy informed.

Examining the literature of collective activism Dominique Caouette (2006) summarizes three variables that explain the rise and outcomes of contemporary transnational activism. Namely, Internationalization, political opportunities and the emergence of cosmopolitan activists. Internationalization is manifested in the growth of international institutions and the fostered linkages between local, national and international organizations. Upon the interaction between compound internationalization and domestic bodies, multiple political opportunities arise. Which lead to the emergence of a breed of activists that she describes as: “fluid, cosmopolitan, but rooted layer of activists and advocates”. (Caouette, 2006)

Applying this theoretical narrative to IFCN, there are a few things could be observed. First, IFCN didn’t arise in a vacuum. It came as a by-product of the work of local actors in the US (Poynter) who after multiple years of local fact-checking decided to take the initiative and go beyond the borders of the United States. Caouette believes that “Transnational activists are very seldom working at the transnational level exclusively. Instead, they tend to be “rooted” at local and national levels” (Caouette, 2006) which is proved to be the case in IFCN. Second, internationalization and interaction between similar actors within different geographical boundaries has led to stronger tendencies to organize collective action and have a new institution that facilitates movement of information, minimize transaction cost and create a sustainable institutional memory. As a transnational activist network, IFCN through its annual summit attempted to provide a platform for journalists, activists, and scholars to meet and explore how they could work better towards driving more scrutiny on politicians and media around the world. The casual communication through the email group has also made it a lot easier to

exchange more information about how to be better fact-checkers, collect data for further study of the evolution of fact-checking, or even directly to harness group psychological support.

Keck and Sikkink identified four approaches to politics that advocacy networks use to be impactful. Namely: Information Politics, Symbolic Politics, Leverage Politics and finally Accountability Politics. The most two prominent approaches for IFCN are information and accountability politics.

First, Information is important as it links network members and it is paramount for the efficiency of the network. The power of the network lies in its ability to provide information that would otherwise not be available, from sources that do not have enough opportunities to be heard. This is specifically more important when actors are geographically distant and separated (Keck and Sikkink, 1999). As the IFCN connects fact-checkers globally, it does serve this purpose by facilitating information flow, providing actors in different countries with information necessary for their daily operation and also for their strategic development. Barriers to getting the right information to gain influence are minimized as the brand of IFCN acts as a vouching power that others relate to.

Second, Accountability politics are at the core of what fact-checkers globally do on a daily basis. They use discursive positions of governments along with their information capabilities to expose the gap between what is supposed to happen and what is actually happening. (Keck and Sikkink, 1999).

In conclusion, this chapter tried to explore the globalism of fact-checking through an argument of evolution. Fact-checking is no longer a US centered phenomenon, the birth of the IFCN is proof to this. IFCN can be looked upon through different theoretical lenses. From an institutional perspective, the IFCN is an institution with the primary function of minimizing transaction cost and managing information flow between various members globally. While from a global advocacy perspective, the IFCN is a Transnational Advocacy Network coordinating a continuous international campaign against political lying and encouraging the effective use of journalism as a tool to hold politicians accountable and keep democracy informed.

CHAPTER IV

IMPACT

This chapter will ponder through the question: What type of influence does fact checking have? And how this influence can be measured? First, the concept of slacktivism would be explored; light would be shed on the different aims of fact-checking, a look into existing frameworks of impact-assessment and propose a two-level framework of looking into fact-checking impact both nationally and transnationally.

Fact-checking: Slacktivism or Activism?

From a US perspective, the year 2012 proved to be historical for fact-checking from two conflicting perspectives. On one hand, the 2012 U.S presidential race proved to be “the most fact-checked electoral contest in American history” (Graves and Glaisyer, 2012). On the other, It was the year of Fact Check attack as a discussion on fact-checking efficacy was circulating and received attention from the mainstream press. (Amazeen, 2013) This has led to a discussion over the efficacy of fact-checking while fact-checking organizations were steadily growing.

Figure 7. Number of Fact-checking initiatives created every year from 1995 - 2016 . Produced from compiling data from *Fact-checkers database*, by Duke Reporters' Lab, 2016.

This bar chart illustrates the number of fact-checking organisations founded on a yearly basis from 1995 to 2016. It can be seen that globally the years 2014, and 2015 have witnessed the greatest number of new fact-checking organisations at 31 organisations in both years. The global explosion seems to have started 2010 onwards. Overall, we can see a clear upward trend in the number of fact-checking organisations founded year to year.

With the accelerating rise of technology and the exponential disruption in communication, it has become easier than ever to mobilize people for causes, attract more people to political participation and strive for real impact on the political and democratic process. However, this has also led to a subtle debate on the emergence of Slacktivism. Slacktivism is explained by Evgeny Morozov (2009) as any political activity that has zero contribution to real political life or with no social impact that only helps increasing the feel-good feeling of participants. For him, Slacktivism resembles “an illusion of having a meaningful impact” (Morozov, 2009). Morozov’s fear is that the digital revolution maybe only pushing us from the idea of true democratization and building a viable effective global civil society towards a world with lazy actors who get passive satisfaction from indulgence into meaningless activities with little value in the real world. (Morozov, 2009)

On the other hand of the debate, some argue that even slacktivism in its purest forms may have a value. First, the concept of slacktivism is often based on a simple idea: The surge of awareness around a certain cause "is in and of itself a worthy reason to pursue them." (Seay, 2014, para. 3). A recent study by Barberá et al. (2015) confirms that online engagement had a significant role to play in transforming a demonstration into a social movement. Their conclusion locates the power of “slacktivism” in the fact that it enhances the exposure of the cause from a few active, angry citizens to thousands of people all over the world with just a few clicks and manages to build a network quickly (Barberá et al., 2015). This claim is also furtherly substantiated by another study by Kirk Kristofferson, Katherine White and John Peloza (2014) which focused on “How the Social Observability of an Initial Act of Token Support Affects Subsequent Prosocial Action”. The study concludes through a series of experiments that slacktivism leads to sometimes further deep engagement in the real world. (Kristofferson, White, & Peloza, 2014)

While this is more obvious in online campaigns, where all you are required to do is to join a Facebook group, sign an online petition or even change your Facebook profile picture, the question is: Does fact-checking constitute a form of online Slacktivism where fact-checkers think they are actually impacting their political surrounding without any substantial evidence? Is fact-checking only meaningful to the community of fact-checkers and niche of journalists or does it extend beyond this to bring about more tangible and immediate change in the behavior of media and politicians?

This can be evaluated by examining different attempts to trace the influence of fact-checking, but first, we have to understand the different aims of fact-checking to be able to follow the influence accurately.

Fact-checking: Diverse Aims, Diverse Forms of Impact

Deciding whether and how fact-checking brings about change or make a difference is one of the most challenging tasks, partly due to the novelty of the

phenomenon, and partly because of the different aims of fact-checking. While fact-checking organizations strive to provide facts to the public, they do this for sometimes different reasons. For example, for some, it is about informing democracy and for others, it is about increasing citizen engagement in the public sphere and promoting accountability. Some believe it helps to improve the public debate and others believe it advances journalism practices.

This observed diversity confirmed through three different manifestations: literature, interviews, and existing mission statements.

First, throughout existing literature different perspectives could be viewed. For example, a study by Elizabeth et al. (2015) revealed that nearly around 65% of the population of the survey which consisted of graduates of communication and journalism, across two different generations believed that fact-checking is an effective form of journalism (American Press Institute, 2015, para. 2). This reflects a perception of fact-checking within practitioners of journalism; that it is an evolution of journalism in response to the chaos of misinformation. This diversity of aims and audiences is also captured by Lucas Graves and Tom Glaisyer (2012) in their US focused paper “The Fact-Checking Universe in Spring 2012” where they maintain that Fact-checkers address more than one audience, and they strive to fulfill more than one aim. On one hand, they provide information with the goal of helping the masses to make more efficient choices at the ballot box. On the other hand, they address a second, smaller audience, mainly the public figures they monitor and of other political journalists (Graves and Glaisyer, 2012).

Second, through the conducted interviews, different aims and ways of impact assessment were captured. For example: in my interview with Bill Adair he confirmed this diversity when I asked him about how they assess their impact he stated:

“I have a different standard than a lot of fact-checkers here, they see their role as stopping falsehoods, getting politicians to stop lying, my goal is simply to inform democracy. I want to give the voter the information they need to make wise decisions. but I recognize that the voter may disagree with my conclusion [...] so I don't measure our success with how often politicians correct themselves.” (Adair, personal communication, June 10, 2016)

Third, by going through mission statements of existing fact-checking organizations, the contrast could be captured. For example, FactCheck.org states that its mission is to provide accurate information to improve public discourse and eventually yield a better-informed public: “Our goal is to apply the best practices of both journalism and scholarship, and to increase public knowledge and understanding”. Others like Argentina's fact-checking organization Chequeado strives to address the three aims previously mentioned: “to improve public discourse; to encourage political accountability and to promote citizen participation” (Pomares and Guzmán, 2015, p. 2)

In conclusion, different fact-checking organizations don't address all actors equally (political leaders, journalists, and citizens). Some have more results-oriented approaches than others. Some focus on the process while others are more concerned with the results yielded. Hence, efforts of measuring the influence of fact-checking organizations need to take the diversity of its aims into account.

Impact Assessment Frameworks

Several attempts of establishing theoretical frameworks of impact assessment for fact-checking exist. A useful framework for impact assessment is explored by Michelle A. Amazeen (2013); where she looked at three main areas of impact assessment: the way fact-checking influences the public, political operatives, and journalism. The way fact-checking influences the public can be measured through proxies of voter knowledge, accessibility, and voter engagement. Influencing political operatives can be looked upon through accountability (Amazeen, 2013).

Alternatively, Graves and Glasiyer (2012) provided three mechanisms through which fact-checking works: First, changing people's minds by validating false claims about any given issue, fact-checking offers relevant facts and encourages people to question falsehoods. Second, changing journalism: by putting more emphasis on the role of journalists not only as information transmitters but also validators. Third, changing the conversation: by highlighting and exposing political lying and deception, fact-checking increases the cost of lying and pressures political figures to refrain from disseminating falsehoods in the future. (Graves and Glaisyer, 2012)

A different angle of looking into the impact of fact-checking organizations could be proposed here; by looking through the impact they exert on two primary levels: nationally and transnationally. Nationally, fact-checking can have immediate and tangible results affecting the different actors; public and political operatives, and also a soft long-term impact by normalizing fact-checking and rooting it down the popular culture of societies. Transnationally, by looking at the way through which one fact-checking organization have a direct and indirect impact on creating other fact-checking organization, encouraging cooperation and advancing the movement itself.

Impact Nationally and Transnationally

The most straight-forward way of looking into impact is to look at actions triggered by fact-checking in their operating environment. How did media and political operatives behave after being fact-checked? Did they alter their behavior? Did they provide apologies or corrections? The behavior can vary from accepting or rejecting the fact-check, to denying responsibility or in the best scenarios apologizing and adapting or dropping the statement. The biggest limitation in assessing the impact of fact-checking is the mere fact that you cannot know what lies are not told today because of fact-checking, which downplays the impact of fact-checking.

Another important yet often ignored impact is the way through which fact-checking gets rooted down in the popular culture of societies. Moving from a prevailing culture of collective naivety to a dominant culture of healthy skepticism towards news does not happen overnight. It is a continuous process molded by the daily practice of democracy, healthiness of political systems and for sure the fact-checking organisations that strive to empower citizens with facts across different political spectrums. One proxy of understanding the cultural shift from naivety to skepticism is to try to capture the way fact-checking culture becomes rooted in the popular culture of society. In other words, the process of normalization of healthy skepticism towards media and news as a daily ritual.

Michael Schudson understands popular culture broadly as “beliefs and practices, and the objects through which they are organized, that are widely shared among a population” (Schudson, 1987, p. 51). Rachel Wayne (2014) attributes the importance of popular culture study to the way it helps us “reveal the underlying assumptions, power structures, and philosophical and moral constructs of the society that produces those cultural products” (Wayne, 2014). Beyond the traditional role of journalism through the lens of the Information-Transmission Model; through which the mission of journalism was to transmit information as they are without doing the extra work, fact-checking can be incorporated in the popular beliefs of society and evolve from being an elitist phenomenon to a more rooted down behavior in everyday life.

Fact-checking and Popular Culture

As fact-checking growth is considered a very recent, under-researched and modern phenomenon, the author tried to look for evidence and examples of fact-checking organisations becoming more adopted in popular culture through TV, comics, songs, statements and other manifestations of popular culture. These expressions can be considered as signs of the possibility of mass and the gradual adoption of fact-checking. Some of these manifestations are explored in detail below, in Egypt, the United States and Iran.

First, in Egypt, Abbas Adel, the founder of MorsiMeter pointed out that after the emergence of the MorsiMeter, shortly it has been used as a cultural reference in comics, jokes, satire programs and even a pop song by an underground singer Ramy Essam with the title of MorsiMeter came into existence. (Adel, personal communication, 8 June 2016) The significance of this adoption is that it takes such initiatives outside their limited sphere of influence to become a reference to a larger audience. When Abdel-Fatah Elsisy came to power in Egypt, the team behind did not create a SisiMeter. However, three other initiatives with the name of SisiMeter came to existence. Despite lacking any fact-checking methodology or goals, the fact that other independent groups immediately borrowed the name of the MorsiMeter to document some of the alleged crimes of the military coup in Egypt shows that MorsiMeter had created a growing culture of fact-checking that manifested modestly when the right opportunity came.

Second, in the United States, the examples of incorporating fact-checking in popular culture are numerous. Mark Stencel, Co-Director of the Duke Reporters' Lab pointed out that fact-checking got a nice shout-out from Stephen Colbert in November 2015. On November 20th episode of CBS's The Late Show, Colbert delivered a two-minute commentary on an incident and at the end he shouted: "Washington Post, fact-check me." in reference to the Washington Post fact-checking arm. (Stencel, personal communication, 08 June 2016)

Bill Adair, Knight Professor of the Practice of Journalism and Public Policy at Duke University, also pointed out that also similar statements came from politicians. For example:

“Governor Chris Christie of New Jersey, Marco Rubio of Florida, former governor Jeb Bush of Florida, all of them have used the phrase ‘politifacted’. Jeb Bush said: I’m going to be careful here because I’m going to be politifacted, when he was talking about one statistic. What does that tell you?

He was more careful, because he knows we are out there.” (Adair, personal communication, August 2, 2016)

He also pointed out that PolitiFact and the Truth-O-Meter have been featured in several comic strips and political cartoons. In his words: “Last week, we were featured in the comic strip XKCD, which is popular with the tech community in the US, in several political cartoons, including one on Lie of the Year ” (Adair, personal communication, August 2, 2016)

In the realm of Satire comedy, Politifact has been featured on the Daily Show with Jon Stewart and The Colbert Report and On John Oliver’s show on HBO the biggest two satire shows in America. The Daily Show alone has a viewership of more than one million. The figure is also similar to the one of The Colbert Report at around 1.2 million.

Third, In Iran, Farhad Souzanchi, from the team of Rouhani Meter pointed out that a prominent Iranian cartoonist, Nikahang Kowsar depicted Rouhani as Pinocchio with his nose being measured for its length with a caption dedicating this cartoon to "the Rouhani Meter folks" (Kowsar, 2014)

As simple as these examples might seem, they constitute an indication of how fact-checking is bringing about soft change in the local popular culture and the way it promotes a culture of consciousness and responsibility on the politicians’ end and healthy skepticism on the public’s end.

Case Study: From the MorsiMeter to the Global Meter

An increasing theme over the last three decades is global interconnectedness which has influenced lives of people in every dimension. The definition of globalization remains controversial as the literature is full of competing definitions. However, a broad-ranging definition maintains that it is “the growing interconnectedness and interrelatedness of all aspects of society” (Jones, 2006, p. 2). This interconnectedness had its influence on the growth of fact-checking globally. Distance is becoming more and more irrelevant as it becomes easier through technology to observe, learn and interact.

Bill Adair started PolitiFact in the United States out of frustration in 2007; it assessed the truthiness of statements of politicians in addition to determining the degree to which Obama sticks to his promises. After five years, a team of two in Egypt were inspired by it to start independently “MorsiMeter”; the first promise-tracking and presidential accountability venture in Egypt created one day after having the first democratically elected president. Egypt at this time, was believed to be in a transition phase from authoritarianism to democracy.

Impact on the National Level

The MorsiMeter as an accountability tool was launched the same day of the presidential announcement and even before inauguration. It capitalized on the existing polarization to create a fierce public debate. This comes to a country where “you were afraid to whisper the name of the president for thirty years” (Adel, personal communication, 20 August 2016). Evidence suggests that this attempt was successful. First, the initiative was considered a non-partisan source providing information to media about what has been accomplished versus what was promised.

Second, it was adopted by the Egyptian presidency. Adel, the founder of MorsiMeter, mentioned that the presidential team was almost reporting to the MorsiMeter team. A precedence that shows that at least certain level of official adoption was there, instead of denial or confrontation (Adel, personal communication, 20 August 2016). In that sense, the introduction of promise tracking into Egyptian politics seems to have scrutinized accountability at that time. Third, as explained earlier, the MorsiMeter made its way to the popular culture by being portrayed in comics, satire programs, and even songs.

Impact on the Transnational Level

The people behind the MorsiMeter did not know as well that they would be the direct reason of inspiring at least two other fact-checking organisations: The Iranian Rouhani Meter and the Canadian TrudeauMetre. The about page of RohaniMeter states:

“Rouhani Meter is a project that aims to monitor the accomplishment of promises made by Iranian President Hassan Rouhani. It is inspired by Morsi Meter, which was created by a group of young Egyptians to observe the actions taken by then Egyptian president, Mohamed Morsi, towards the promises that he had made. Rouhani Meter is an independent project which initially benefited from the support of the University of Toronto.” (“About the Rouhani Meter”, 2016)

similarly, the about page of tradeauMetre maintains that:

“The inspiration for this website comes from a similar one that was done by Egyptian activists back in 2012. I've had the great opportunity to travel to the place several times and try to keep up with the news coming from there. At the time, Egyptians had just chosen their first democratically-elected president - Mohamed Morsi - and some smart people started a website called the Morsi Meter. I modeled this website after theirs. What struck me at the time was that no Western country that I know of had ever done something similar - simple, collaborative, unbiased, and user-friendly. Maybe It is because we take our democracy for granted - maybe It is because we don't care - but whatever the reason was, I felt we were missing a great opportunity to come back to the roots of what living in a democratic society means. It often takes the courage of those who face difficult circumstances to inspire the rest of us to action, and this is what happened in this case.” (“TrudeauMetre”, 2016)

This butterfly effect could have also happened elsewhere and may also explain why global fact-checking grew up 50% in past year. (Stencel, 2016)

Figure 8. New fact-checking sites by region in the year 2015 - 2016. Produced from compiling data from *Fact-checkers database*, by Duke Reporters' Lab, 2016.

The founders of the MorsiMeter created the Global Meter, going beyond the borders of Egypt; which their own website defines as:

“GlobalMeter is an expansion of MorsiMeter project, which started in Egypt after the first democratic elections, post revolution, aiming to track the promises of Ex-president Mohamed Morsi in his first 100 days. The success of the project, urged the team to think of taking the idea globally to enable everyone across the globe to track the promises of their politicians” (“Global Meter”, 2016)

In essence, they export the software they built to monitor their president, to other countries. The motivation behind this was to give a helping hand to those who want to do the same in Egypt and help create a global culture of political accountability. In their words they state:

“Most of the times, such promises are unrealistic and only used for propaganda and gaining votes in the elections. The project aims at creating a public memory that pushes politicians to fulfill their promises and hold them accountable to it. Thus, making future politicians promise only what they can do and avoid manipulation of the crowds through media campaigns that provides unrealistic and non-achievable programs and promises.” (“Global Meter”, 2016)

The first Global Meter based venture was in Tunisia monitoring the performance of Mehdi Jomaa, Former Prime Minister of Tunisia. A few other meters followed as the Tunisian situation developed and brought a new president and prime minister who were both monitored through other two websites based on the Global Meter. By observation, the sites seemed inactive as the partner group in Tunisia faced challenges in using the tool to initiate a relevant public debate.

In this capacity, the MorsiMeter has started directly three different fact-checking organisations outside Egypt and indirectly influenced two others to model their promise-trackers upon the Egyptian one. It is also worth noting that the American Obama-O-Meter inspired the MorsiMeter itself.

In conclusion, impact assessment of fact-checking is challenging due to the novelty of the phenomenon and the diversity of its goals. Evidence suggest that fact-checking is not an act of slacktivism and adoption of fact-checking in popular culture can be a proxy of its slow and long-term impact. Also the work fact-checkers do in one country, easily influences others in other countries which clearly advances the phenomenon globally in an organic, non-preplanned way. It also sets the bar of what is becoming increasingly standard and makes it relatable to new communities.

CONCLUSION

This study has attempted to answer the central question of How fact-checking evolved to become a global phenomenon with direct impact on national and transnational politics? In trying to respond to this question a few questions came to existence including What are the different trends of fact-checking globally? Is fact-checking exclusive for journalists? Does fact-checking constitute a manifestation of Slacktivism or does it bring about real impact?

The study explained this through two main arguments: the distribution and evolution of the movement. Regarding distribution the scene today is more diversified than ever before. Fact-checking has taken different forms whether through the internet or TV, whether targeting one politician, a group of politicians or even media, whether they are classic fact-checking initiatives, promise trackers or hybrid of both. Today, there are more than 157 fact-checking organizations globally in around 55 countries. Those countries do not belong to one separate category. They range from developed to developing, from free to non-free from democratic to autocratic. Evidence that indicates the globalism of the phenomenon.

Regarding evolution, the study looked at the increasing cooperation between different fact-checkers around the world and explained it through theoretical lenses of institutions and Transnational Advocacy Networks (TANs). The International Fact-Checking Network (IFCN) is a by-product of the evolution of fact-checking globally which not only aims at increasing cooperation but also softly regulating fact-checking by promoting standards, ethics, and innovation in fact-checking. Also, evidence that indicates the globalism of the phenomenon.

Although misinformation has always existed in the world of media and politics, Internet has given it substance and visibility. Identifying the truth is an ever-increasing difficult process, and it is a task maintained by a minority of Vanguard. Fact-checking by definition is always in the defense position trying to correct misinformation and control damage. The recent phenomenon which has initially flourished in the US has grown beyond its borders and taken different forms globally. Although initially perceived as exclusively a progression of ethical journalism, it has captured the interest of entrepreneurs, civil society and citizens who started some fact-checking organisations in different parts of the world.

Technology has bred a new generation of political observatories that uses technology to advance the public information ecosystem. Fact-checking boomed in the US since 2004 and came to be controversial in 2012. Ever since it has captured some interest of researchers and scholars. Most literature focused on the American context and the journalism angle. Through employing relevant scholarly literature and upon critical analysis of the available data and interviews made, this study concludes that Fact-checking has evolved from an unorganized phenomenon mostly associated with one country (US), to become a global network and institutionalized trend that advances globally. It has also gone beyond its journalism divide to include others like civil society groups, citizens, and entrepreneurs.

Evidence suggests that fact-checking has both impacts on the national and transnational levels. Additional evidence suggests that fact-checking is slowly being adopted by popular culture in different areas of the world bringing about a soft yet steady change towards a healthy skepticism against media and politics.

There are however limitations to this study. First, The study counted mainly on data produced by two groups (Duke Reporters' Lab and International Fact-checking Network). Throughout the research process, the author came across some other fact-checking organisations that are not covered by this data. So while this data tells us something about fact-checkers around the world, it is certainly not inclusive of everyone. Second, a general limitation to understanding impact is the fact that we cannot retrospectively assess the damage that would be inflicted if it was not for fact-checking. In other words, we can not know what lies are not told today because of fact-checking, which downplays the impact of fact-checking. Third, quantification of this impact remains questionable and is beyond the scope of this study as the study did not pursue a strictly quantitative approach. Finally, Further questions that can be researched and gaps to be filled include: Are fact-checking organisations led by journalists different than those run by people not affiliated to journalism? Do they offer better quality? Are they more sustainable? How can we quantitatively assess the impact of fact-checking? These questions are important as they delve into understanding how the backgrounds of different fact-checkers influence the impact of their organisations.

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